

1 HSV-1 ICP22 antagonizes telomerase reverse transcriptase (TERT) function.

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7 The HSV-1 genome contains dozens of viral gene products. We measured total transcription by
8 RNA-sequencing in human cells expressing doxycycline-inducible ICP22 to discover novel functions and
9 network interaction partners of ICP22. We describe here control of TERT by ICP22.

10 Citations

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